

BC-SIM-PL-007

SIMBIO-SYS Checkout#04b

Test Summary

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope

In this document we describe all the tests to be performed during the Instrument CheckOut (ICO) # 04b for the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem (SIMBIO-SYS).

1.2. Reference Document

- [RD.1]** BC-SIM-TN-003_-_Reports_and_Note_Layout_and_Flow,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179)
- [RD.2]** BC-SIM-GAF-MA-002 10 001 – SIMBIO-SYS User Manual
- [RD.3]** BC-SIM-TR-033_-_VIHI_ICO#04_report
- [RD.4]** BC-SIM-TR-035_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#04_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.5281/zenodo.10014954](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10014954)
- [RD.5]** BC-SIM-TR-034_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#04_Interchannel_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.5281/zenodo.8366159](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8366159)
- [RD.6]** BC-SIM-PL-006_-_SIMBIO-SYS_Checkout_04_Test_Summary_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/204](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/204)
- [RD.7]** BC-SIM-TN-008_-_SIMBIO-SYS_FOP_update_after_ICO#02,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/162](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/162)
- [RD.8]** BC-ASD-SP-00176

1.3. Acronyms

APID	Application Process IDentifier
ASW	Application SoftWare
CSV	Comma Separated Values
FPA	Focal Plane Assembly

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FOP	Flight Operation Procedure
HK	HouseKeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
ICO	Instrument CheckOut
LFB	Low Freq Behaviour
ME	Main Electronics
NECP	Near Earth Commissioning Phase
OBCP	On-Board Control Procedure
POR	Payload Direct Operation Request
PDS	Planetary Data System
PE	Proximity Electronics
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PSC	Packet Sequence Control
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem
SSC	Source Sequence Count
STC	STereo imaging Channel
TC	Telecommand
TEC	Thermo-Electric Cooler
TM	Telemetry
VIHI	VIisible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

1.4. Document format and Repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD.1] and will be archived on the SIMBIO-SYS ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=SIMBIO-SYS>), on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

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1.5. Document Organization

This document is organized in sections whose topics are listed as follows:

- Section 2 – ICO#04b objective, with a brief description (see Section 8.2.2 of [RD.2] for details) of the functional tests we are going to execute
- Section 3 – ICO#04b implementation and validation, with:
 - a brief description of which Flight Operation Procedures (FOPs) and Payload Operation Requests (PORs) we are going to use to perform the required test
 - the results of the sequence validation using a Simulation Software developed within the team
 - an estimation of the required resources in terms of Data Volume, duration and expected number of frames for each sequence
- Section 4 – ICO#04b timeline, with the list of activities to be performed logically ordered to optimize instrument activations and test duration

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2. Test objective

The scope of the SIMBIO ICO#04b is the repetition of a significant part of ICO#04 tests due to an erroneous commanding of the VIHI channel. In particular, the SIMBIO-SYS team has requested to repeat:

1. VIHI Performance Test, that was interrupted due to the wrong commanding (see [RD.3] and Issue 8 of [RD.4] for details)
2. SIMBIO-SYS Interchannel Test, that was partially executed since the VIHI channel was powered-off for safety during the execution of its Performance Test (see [RD.5] for details)

2.1. Performance Test

During the ICO#04b the only the VIHI performance shall be verified by repeating the execution of the VIHI ICO#04 test with the verification of its general performances and the operability of its major subsystems (TEC, Detector, Shutter, Lamp and LED) – see [RD.6] for details.

2.2. Interchannel Test

As described in [RD.6], the goal of this test is to verify:

1. a possible dependence of the Low Frequency Behaviour (LFB) with respect to the Repetition Time (RT) parameter of the Science TC of the cameras
2. the presence of such fluctuation also on the VIHI channel and its influence on the cameras

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3. Test implementation

3.1. Tools

Tests reported in the following sub-sessions shall be executed by means of proper FOPs, On-Board Control Procedures (OBCPs) and PORs listed in the following subsections and described in [RD.7], [RD.8] and Annexed files.

3.2. Available resources

As per ESA-ESOC official communication by Silvano Manganelli emails, the SIMBIO-SYS ICO#04b test will take place on 24/04/2021 at 08:00:00 UTC and the available time and Data-Volume resources will be:

- test duration: 8 hours
- Data-Volume: 150 Mbytes

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3.3. SIMBIO-SYS Performance Tests

3.3.1. VIHI Performance Test

3.3.1.1. Scope

The test will be the repetition of the one planned in [RD.6] with the appropriate corrections that produced the errors during the ICO4 (see [RD.3] for details).

3.3.1.2. Preparation

To execute this test SIMBIO-SYS shall be in the following status:

Unit	Status
ME	OFF (on the MAIN channel)
HRIC	OFF
STC	OFF
VIHI	OFF

Waiting for SIMBIO-SYS ME Application SoftWare (ASW) update which should also affect the parameters for the correct TEC activation, a dedicated TCs sequence has been prepared to upload the nominal TEC parameters. With reference to the **ESA-ESOC recommendation on the POR generation for the ICOs activities** (i.e., minimize the number of produced PORs to simplify their import and verification) this sequence has been included in the POR used for the test (see initialization step in following section).

3.3.1.3. Description

A POR with **SPOT ID BPSS00791** and named **SIMBIOSYS_VIHI_ICO#04bis_test** has been prepared which contains the following operations (in bold the difference with respect to the wrong sequence run during ICO#04):

1. VIHI Power On and initialisation (TEC parameters upload)
2. Dark Frame Acquisition; Dark storage and no Dark Subtraction
3. Dark Frame Acquisition; **no** Dark storage and Dark Subtraction.
4. Dark Frame Acquisition; **no** Dark storage and Dark Subtraction;

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5. Dark Frame Acquisition; Dark storage; no Dark Subtraction
6. Power ON LAMP
7. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction and IBR=0
8. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, no Dark subtraction and IBR=32
9. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x1 and IBR=0
10. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x1 and IBR=32
11. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x1 and IBR=63
12. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x2 and IBR=0
13. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x2 and IBR=32
14. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x2 and IBR=63
15. Power OFF LAMP
16. Power Off VIHI

3.3.1.4. Validation

The POR **SIMBIOSYS_VIHI_ICO#04bis_test** has been validated by means of a Simulation Software and produces the following results:

Sequence duration		00:31:32			
Sequence Data Volume					
-	ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI	Overall
Science	-	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.0906 [Gb]	0.0906 [Gb]
HK	0.0179 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.6808 [Mb]	0.6986 [Mb]
Total	0.0179 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.0913 [Gb]	0.0913 [Gb]

To note that above resources computation have to be considered as upper limits since for their computation the Simulation Software needs to introduce some fake TCs (i.e., ME and channel switch-on) in order to reproduce the correct SIMBIO-SYS state for the analysis.

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3.3.1.5. Expected Science data

In the following table it is reported the number of frames that are expected to be produced during the test:

HRIC		STC		VIHI	
TC	# frames	TC	# frames	TC	# frames
				1	23
				2	23
				3	18
				4	9
				5	9
				6	9
				7	5
				8	5
				9	5
				10	2
				11	2
				12	2
				-	112

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3.4. SIMBIO-SYS Interchannel Test

3.4.1. Scope

The aim of this test is to evaluate if the detector reset fluctuation is present also on the VIHI channel, if the VIHI operations influence the fluctuation on both the HRIC and STC channels and if such effect depends, on the two cameras, by the RT parameter contained in their Science TC.

3.4.2. Preparation

To execute this test SIMBIO-SYS shall be in the following status:

Unit	Status
ME	ON (on the MAIN channel)
HRIC	OFF
STC	OFF
VIHI	OFF

See Section 3.3.1.2.

3.4.3. Description

A POR with **SPOT ID BPSS00793** and named **SIMBIO-SYS_ALL_ICO#04bis_interference_test** has been prepared which contains the following operations:

1. HRIC, STC power on and initialization and VIHI switch-on/off
2. the TC sequence for the TECs parameters upload
3. HRIC, STC and VIHI Science acquisitions with different combination of RT

To be compliant with the reduced available resources (mainly DataVolume), for the two cameras the following configuration shall be considered:

- HRIC: 256x256 pixels window, IBR=8 and RT=1s for 5' and RT=1.5s for 7'
- STC: filterX window (i.e., 64x128 pixels), IBR=8 and RT=1s

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3.4.4. Validation

The POR **SIMBIO-SYS_ALL_ICO#04bis_interference_test** has been validated by means of a Simulation Software and produces the following results:

Sequence duration		01:25:10			
Sequence Data Volume					
-	ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI	Overall
Science	-	0.038 [Gb]	0.006 [Gb]	0.012 [Gb]	0.058 [Gb]
HK	0.0640 [Mb]	0.078 [Mb]	0.071 [Mb]	0.048 [Mb]	0.262 [Mb]
Total	0.0640 [Mb]	0.038 [Gb]	0.006[Gb]	0.012 [Mb]	0.058 [Gb]

To note that above resources computation have to be considered as upper limits since for their computation the Simulation Software needs to introduce some fake TCs (i.e., ME and channel switch-on) in order to reproduce the correct SIMBIO-SYS state for the analysis.

3.4.4.1. Expected Science data

In the following table it is reported the number of frames that are expected to be produced during the test:

HRIC		STC		VIHI	
TC	# frames	TC	# frames	TC	# frames
1	299	1	719	1	1439
2	280	2	721		
3	300				
4	280				
-	1159	-	1440	-	1439

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4. Timeline

With reference to the tests described in the previous sections, the following timeline applies:

ID	Description	Estimated duration	Estimated Data Volume	XML file
1. SIMBIOSYS_VIHI_ICO#04bis_test	VIHI nominal TEC parameters upload and VIHI performance verification with nominal operative parameters	00:31:32	0.0913 [Gb]	× BPSS00791_00203.BC
2. SIMBIO-SYS_ALL_ICO#04bis_interference_test	Channels nominal TEC parameters upload and Science acquisitions in several RT configurations	01:25:10	0.0559 [Gb]	× BPSS00793_00201.BC